

LEGAL POLITICAL RECONSTRUCTION OF VILLAGE BOUNDARIES: THE URGENCY OF THE PRINCIPLE OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLES' PARTICIPATION AND ITS IMPACT ON LEGAL CERTAINTY

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ABSTRACT

It is urgent to carry out a political reconstruction of village boundaries to ensure policies that accommodate indigenous peoples as legal and social entities that have rights to their territories; The principle of legal certainty must be viewed not only from the legal-formal aspects of government, but also from the social legitimacy provided by indigenous communities; The urgency of indigenous peoples' participation is a form of political reconstruction of the law of village boundaries which aims to replace a top-down approach that is administratively biased with a bottom-up approach that respects local wisdom; The final goal of this research is to formulate an integrative and participatory political and legal model in the determination of village boundaries that guarantees double legal certainty (state law and customary law); The main legal basis includes the 1945 Constitution Article 18B Paragraph (2) and Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages; and its derivatives of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 45 of 2016 concerning Guidelines for the Establishment and Affirmation of Village Boundaries; This study uses a normative juridical method with a conceptual and legislative approach; The conflict resolution offered is through mediation and adjudication mechanisms that integrate customary law and participatory cartographic data.

Keywords: *Indigenous Participation Activities, Legal Certainty, Local Wisdom, Legal Politics, Village Boundaries.*